

ASSESSMENT OF ACCESS BANK'S USAGE OF SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORMS AS A STRATEGY FOR ENHANCING CUSTOMER RELATIONS AMONG AAUA STUDENTS

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Abstract: Many organisations, the financial institutions inclusive have adopted the customer relations to enhance engagement, communication and service delivery. Therefore, this study investigated the effectiveness of Access Bank's usage of social media platforms as a tool in fostering customer relations among students at Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko (AAUA) in Ondo state. Hinged on Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Technological Determinism theories, this study adopted the survey method for data collection using Purposive sampling technique to select only respondents that have an account with Access Bank and are also aware of the public relations strategies adopted by the bank. The sample size employed for this study consists of 260 respondents which was drawn from the larger population of 25,000 students at AAUA using Wimmer and Dominick's sample size calculator. Findings revealed that there was a substantial engagement across various platforms, emphasizing the positive influence of the bank's social media activities. Notably, respondents appreciate the faster response times, engaging content, and enhanced customer interaction facilitated by Access Bank's social media engagement. Based on the findings, it is recommended that Access Bank should refine its engagement strategies further by exploring other social media platforms and diversifying content strategy to cater to diverse preferences, such as industry news, financial advice, promotions, and customer success stories, to widen engagement with a broader audience.

Keywords: Customer Relations, Access Bank, Social Media Platforms, Public Relations Practitioner

Introduction

Over the years, the media landscape has dramatically changed with traditional media supplemented or totally replaced by social media (Yu et al, 2013). Nowadays, people interact with one another more on these platforms

thereby becoming the major way of communicating. Moreso, It has transformed the way individuals as well as businesses interact over the past decade especially after coronavirus lockdown. In many organisations, the focus is usually on determining customer wants or demands and striving to meet them to enhance business continuity. Hence, the need to provide maximum customer satisfaction through customer relations.

According to Mullings (2005) effective customer relations is the most critical approach of any organization wishing to stay in business for a long time. Therefore, while engaging in customer relations strategy, placing customers at the centre of organisational activities can contribute to the success or otherwise of any organisation. This simply means that customers are one of the important reasons why businesses are in business. A favourable and mutually beneficial customer relationship is also vital to any organisation.

Customer relations is about effective relationship and interaction between an organisation and its customers. According to Mullings (2005), customer relations is about developing the most effective interactive customer service strategy to determine and satisfy the needs of both existing and potential consumers. It is a process “that requires businesses to recognize and nurture their relationships with their clients” (Reynolds, 2002: p 11). Customer Relations is an effective customer service activity that involves all communication and service delivery strategies such as taking responsibilities, accountability with which business organisations interface with their customers to enhance customer’s satisfaction (Sanda, 2006)

Just like other existing businesses, financial institutions are established to cater for customers’ needs to enable them to stay in business. Financial institutions provide financial services for their customers and are regulated by a government authority (Bhole, 2006). Therefore, businesses exist primarily to satisfy customer’s wants and needs in a way that would benefit both the customer and the organisation. Examples of financial institutions include: microfinance banks, building societies, credit unions, commercial and asset management firms and similar businesses.

No doubt, many organisations, the financial institutions inclusive have adopted the customer relations to enhance engagement, communication and service delivery. However, in the digital age, the banking sector has undergone a significant transformation in its approach to customer relations. The use of social media in the banking industry is a relatively recent but rapidly evolving phenomenon that offers numerous advantages in terms of customer engagement, communication, and service delivery. This shift is largely attributed to the widespread adoption of social media platforms as a means to connect and engage with customers. The advent of platforms like Facebook, Twitter, Email, Online chats, Instagram, and LinkedIn enable individuals' voices to be heard (Hong, 2012). Banks have recognized the potential of harnessing these channels to enhance customer relations to build relationships with their customers (Econsultancy, 2013).

Organisations in Nigeria have sought to exploit the opportunities presented by high internet penetration rates and heavy usage of social media. Among the sectors that have embraced social media in the financial services sector. This realisation necessitates the need for financial institutions to have public relations or customer affairs/communication departments that manage and respond to the two-way forms of communications and challenges between the organisation and it’s publics, customers inclusive as success or failure of banks depends, to a large extent, on the usage of social media platforms for customer relations. Therefore, the study focuses on

investigating the effectiveness of Access Bank's usage of social media platforms in fostering customer relations among students at Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko (AAUA) in Ondo state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The level of competition in the banking industry, to attract more customers both locally and internationally, has intensified enormously. To be able to stand out from competitors, your service needs to be excellent. Similarly, in today's business world, the customer is number one priority. This makes it necessary for organisations to provide unique products and services and participate in customer engagement to keep up with their consumers' and endless demands.

In the modern digital landscape, businesses have harnessed the power of social media to establish meaningful connections with customers and elevate the quality of customer relations. In an era characterized by increasing digitisation and the widespread adoption of social media, the banking sector's ability to leverage these platforms to engage with customers is paramount. Though, there have been current discourse on adoption of consumer relations via social media platforms in relation to financial institutions (such as Agboola & Salimon , 2020; Adebowale & Omotayo (2021) only a few studies (such as Olatunji, 2021) explored the nature of the use of social media platforms within the Nigerian banking sector. In the light of this widespread acceptance of social media , discourse on the adoption of social media platforms in the financial world has till date received only scanty academic examination, especially in relation to the focus of this study in the Nigerian context. Therefore, a need exists to bridge this research gap by investigating the specific perceptions and experiences of AAUA students' usage of social media platforms for enhancing customer relations and the extent Access Bank's social media strategies has contributed to customer engagement and relationship management.

Objectives of the Study

This study is guided by the following objectives:

- 1) To find out the social media platforms AAUA students get information about Access Bank the most.
- 2) To investigate the perception of AAUA Students regarding Access Bank's utilization of social media platforms.
- 3) To assess the extent Access Bank's social media customer relationship management has contributed to loyalty to the Bank

Significance of the Study

In an era characterized by increasing digitization and the widespread adoption of social media, the banking sector's ability to leverage these platforms to engage with customers is paramount. This study aims to provide insights into whether Access Bank's strategies align with the preferences and expectations of Akungba residents, contributing to the broader discourse on customer relationship management in the Nigerian banking industry. Findings from the study will be useful resource-materials for prospective scholars in the area of digital media and Business Communication and serve as a guild to public relations practitioners on how to effectively use social media to enhance customer engagement in any financial institutions they represent. This study will also

help banks in Nigeria to enhance customer loyalty and satisfaction, which can contribute to growth in banks' customer base.

Review of Concepts and Literature

Social Media Use in Banking

Businesses today cannot afford to ignore the importance of social media. Social media is a type of online media that expedites conversation when compared to traditional media, which delivers content but does not allow readers/viewers/listeners to participate in the creation and/or development of content (Hensel & Deis, 2010). With over two billion social media users globally, customers have become active participants in in product production, development, marketing, sales, and support (Marques, 2016). Social media in business communication has changed the way organisations conduct business and communicate with their customers. Through the use of social media, organisations can connect with their costumers/ consumers worldwide and also encourage feedbacks from the customers. Social media serve as an advertising vehicles for organisations by positively and negatively impacting organisations' reputation through actions such as "likes" and "tweets" on these platforms (Cadet, 2016).

Statistics has shown that social media usage has increased dramatically over the years (Brandwatch, 2015). In July 2015, the total worldwide population was 7.3 billion with the internet having 3.17 billion users and 2.3 billion active social media users. Internet users had an average of 5.54 social media accounts. Nine years after, in April 2024, there were 5.44 billion internet users worldwide, which amounted to 67.1 percent of the global population (Statista, 2024). The most popular social networking sites include Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, WhatsApp, Instagram and many others. Facebook is considered as the most prominent and popular website with 3.065 million users as at April, 2024 (Cadet, 2016, Statista, 2024). One of the key features on Facebook is the ability for businesses and organisations to create their own pages where individuals can publicly "like" and follow the page of an organisation or brand. This allows creators of such pages to use the feature to engage their followers and pass across latest and important information and developments. Hence, many companies turn to Facebook as an advertising medium because of its high traffic and wider reach (Cadet, 2016).

Evaluating the Effectiveness of Banking Industry's Social Media Usage for Customer Relations

Social media's integration into the banking industry has ushered in a new era of communication and engagement between financial institutions and their customers. Social media platforms serve as direct channels for banks to communicate essential information regarding their services, promotions, and updates. The contemporary banking landscape places considerable emphasis on customer engagement and interaction, and social media platforms have become instrumental in cultivating these relationships. Enhancing customer relations in the banking sector through social media has several key advantages. First and foremost, it allows for personalized communication. As highlighted by Johnson (2018), social media platforms enable banks to tailor their messages and services to individual customers, creating a more personalized and meaningful experience. This level of customization enhances customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The immediacy of social media platforms makes them a valuable channel for customer support and issue resolution. Banks can respond to customer inquiries, address concerns, and resolve problems in real time. The ability to receive direct messages and comments enables banks to engage with customers promptly, resulting in an enhanced service experience (Haron et al., 2018). Banks that excel in social media customer service not only meet customer expectations but also have the opportunity to turn satisfied customers into brand advocates.

Another significant advantage is the increased accessibility of information and services. Social media provides a platform for banks to disseminate important updates, educational content, and self-service options, improving financial literacy among customers (Davis, 2021). This accessibility empowers customers to make informed decisions, fostering trust and confidence in the bank. Furthermore, social media enables real-time interaction and issue resolution. Customers can easily reach out to their bank through social channels to seek assistance or report problems. This immediate responsiveness enhances problem-solving, resulting in higher customer satisfaction and retention (Smith, 2019).

Additionally, social media serves as a valuable tool for gathering feedback and insights from customers, allowing banks to continuously improve their services and products. The use of social media platforms in the banking industry for enhancing customer relations is a significant and evolving trend. With increased adoption, banks can offer personalized communication, improve accessibility to information and services, and provide real-time support and issue resolution. These advantages not only enhance customer satisfaction but also contribute to the long-term success and competitiveness of banks in the modern era.

Effective CRM in banking is also about building and nurturing long-term relationships. It encompasses targeted marketing campaigns that resonate with customers on a personal level. By segmenting their customer base and leveraging CRM data, banks can create tailored marketing efforts. These campaigns are more likely to resonate with specific customer segments and yield positive results. According to Kim, Kim & An (2008), this customer-centric approach is instrumental in enhancing satisfaction levels, as it delivers relevant and valuable content. In turn, satisfied customers are more inclined to stay loyal to the bank and engage in long-term relationships.

Challenges posed by social media use

Data security and privacy are paramount concerns when banking institutions utilize social media platforms. The vast amount of personal and financial data shared on these networks makes them attractive targets for cybercriminals (Gupta, Brooks, & Gupta, 2019). Banking organisations must allocate substantial resources to implement robust cyber security measures, continually monitor threats, and devise incident response plans. Any data breach or security lapse can lead to severe repercussions, including financial losses, reputational damage, and legal liabilities. Banks need to strike a balance between leveraging social media's customer engagement capabilities while ensuring that customer data remains secure.

Reputational risks are amplified in the context of social media. The speed at which information spreads on these platforms can be both a boon and a bane for banks (Duhan, Jayakumar, & Bhaskar, 2013). Positive customer experiences can quickly go viral and enhance the bank's reputation, while negative interactions or complaints can escalate just as rapidly and tarnish it. Managing customer sentiment on social media requires proactive

engagement, prompt issue resolution, and a professional demeanor. Banks must establish clear guidelines for social media interactions and train their staff to handle diverse customer responses effectively.

The volume and pace of customer inquiries and interactions on social media channels can pose operational challenges. Sheth, Sisodia, and Sharma (2021) note that banks must allocate sufficient resources, both in terms of staff and technology, to manage these interactions efficiently. Failure to do so can lead to delayed responses, customer frustration, and potentially lost opportunities for engagement. Additionally, maintaining consistency in responses and ensuring that all customer inquiries are addressed promptly is essential. Banks need well-defined workflows and processes to handle the various types of interactions they may encounter on social media.

In summary, while social media offers numerous benefits for customer engagement, it also presents several challenges and risks for banking institutions. To succeed in the social media landscape, banks must adopt a comprehensive and proactive approach, integrating risk management strategies with customer engagement efforts.

Social Media Strategies in Banking

Social media have become a crucial component of the marketing and communication strategies employed by banks worldwide. To effectively engage with their customers, banks have adopted various strategies which includes content marketing, influencer marketing, interactive content, personalised messaging, real-time customer service, and social listening. Content marketing involves the creation and sharing of relevant, informative, and engaging content on social media platforms to attract and retain customers (Sigala et al., 2019). Banks use this strategy to showcase their expertise, educate customers about financial matters, and build trust.

Another social media strategy widely used by banks is influencer marketing. Banks collaborate with social media influencers, often individuals with significant followings and expertise in finance, to promote their products and services (Khanna & Swaminathan, 2019). These influencers can effectively reach a broad audience and provide authentic reviews and recommendations. By partnering with influencers, banks gain access to their followers, increasing their brand visibility and credibility in the eyes of potential customers.

Customer engagement through social media is a top priority for banks, and they employ strategies such as interactive content and personalized messaging. Interactive content includes quizzes, polls, surveys, and contests, which encourage customer participation and feedback (Khanna & Swaminathan, 2019). These activities not only engage customers but also provide banks with valuable insights into customer preferences and opinions. Personalized messaging involves tailoring communication to individual customers based on their behaviors and interests, enhancing the customer experience (Arndt et al., 2018). Banks use data analytics to segment their audience and deliver targeted content and offers, increasing the likelihood of conversions.

In the digital age, real-time customer service on social media is a critical strategy. Banks use chatbots and dedicated customer service teams to respond to customer inquiries and resolve issues promptly (Ngai et al., 2017). Customers expect quick and efficient responses, and banks that excel in social media customer service can enhance customer satisfaction and loyalty. By leveraging these strategies effectively, banks can establish

themselves as trusted sources of financial information, expand their customer base, and enhance the overall customer experience.

Theoretical Frameworks

This study is anchored on Customer Relationship Management (CRM) and Technological Determinism theories of mass communication. Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a strategic approach that focuses on building and maintaining strong and lasting relationships between organizations and their customers. It involves various processes, technologies, and strategies aimed at understanding customers, meeting their needs, and ultimately fostering customer loyalty (Peppers & Rogers, 1993 as cited in Sisodia, and Sharma, 2021). CRM is a well-established concept developed by scholars and practitioners in the fields of marketing and customer service. It is relevant to the study by providing a solid theoretical framework for evaluating the potentials of social media use on customer relationships in the Nigerian context.

According to Marshall McLuhan's (1963)'s technological determinism technology, the media influences how people think and behave and how societies function as they transition from one technological period to the other (Asak & Ohiagun, 2013). People's behaviour and actions are increasingly influenced by their interactions with digital media. For this research, it is important to consider this idea since it enables us to comprehend how technology has encouraged the use of social media platforms for an effective customer relations in Nigeria and globally. Srinivasan & Rani (2020) highlighted how these technological advancements are reshaping the future of banking by making services more accessible and efficient. New technology has made it possible to relate with diverse customers on a variety of electronic devices at the same time. Put differently, the industry would not have to rely only on conventional mass media to communicate with their customers, instead, it does use the new types of communication platforms provided by social media.

Methodology

This study adopted the survey method to get responses from AAUA students on the effectiveness of Access Bank's usage of social media platforms as a tool in fostering customer relations. The sample size employed for this study consists of 260 participants which were drawn from the larger population of 25,000 students at Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko (according to (www.aaua.edu.ng/about-us)) using Wimmer and Dominick's sample calculator. The population of the study is AAUA students because the study focuses only on Access Bank, Akungba-Akoko branch which is located inside the institution premises which makes the customers of the bank to be predominantly AAUA students. This study adopted purposive sampling technique because only AAUA students who are customers of Access Bank, Akungba were selected as respondents for this study. Structured copies of questionnaire were designed to assess students' perceptions regarding Access Bank's use of social media for customer relations. The questionnaires included Likert scale questions to measure attitudes and perception were administered face-to-face to respondents over a defined period, to ensure consistency in data collection.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Respondents' Responses on the Social Media Platforms Respondents Mostly Use to Get Information about Access Bank the most

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
	47	18%
Twitter	64	25%
Instagram	55	21%
YouTube	44	17%
LinkedIn	50	19%
Total	260	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 1 shows that out of the 260 respondents, most of the respondents, 64 (25%) get information about Access Bank on Twitter followed by the usage of LinkedIn with 50 (19%) respondents. This shows that the major social media platform adopted by Access Bank to disseminate information to its customers is Twitter.

Table 2: Respondents' Responses on the Level of Exposure to Information about Access Bank on Social Media

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Always	100	4%
Sometimes	65	25%
Often	141	54%
Rarely	44	17%
Total	260	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents 47 (18%) agreed that they were often exposed to information about Access Bank, while 65 (25%) respondents were exposed to information about

Access Bank on social media sometimes This shows that majority of the respondents were often exposed to information about Access Bank on social media.

Table 3: Respondents' Responses on the benefits they derive from their exposure to information about Access Bank on Social media platforms

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
I think Access Bank has faster responses on social media	155	55%
I believe there are more engaging content about Access Bank on their social media platforms	180	60%
I believe Access Bank's use of social media platforms enhances customer interaction	168	59%
I think Access Bank's use of social media helps improved clarity in communications	89	38%
I get better news and updates about Financial tips or advice, promotions and offers on Access Bank's social media platforms	70	35%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 3 revealed that majority of the respondents, 180 (60%) believed that Access Bank's presence on media platforms helps in more engaging content, while 155 (55%) respondents admitted that Access Bank social media platforms presence helps in faster response. This means majority of respondents agreed that adoption of social media platforms for customer relations is positive as it helps in faster response, more engaging content, enhanced customer interaction & improved clarity in communications.

Table 4: Respondents Responses to Whether They Feel Valued as a Customer Based on their Interactions with Access Bank on Social Media

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	200	77%
No	60	23%
Total	260	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 4 revealed that 200 (77%) respondents admitted to feeling valued as a customer based on their interactions with Access Bank on social media, and 60 (23%) respondents didn't admitted to feeling valued as a customer based on their interactions with Access Bank on social media. This means that the majority of the respondents admits to feeling valued as a customer based on their interactions with Access Bank on social media.

Table 5: Respondents Responses to If They Are a Loyal Customer As a Result of Access Bank's Social Media Contents For Customer Engagement and Relationship Management

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Yes	230	88%
No	30	12,%
Total	260	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 5 revealed that out of the 260 respondents, 160 (62%) admitted to being a loyal customer as a result of Access Bank's social media contents for customer engagement and relationship management, This means that the majority of the respondents admitted to being loyal customers as a result of Access Bank's social media contents for customer engagement and relationship management.

Table 6: Respondents' Responses The Extent al to Access Bank's Usage of Social Media Platforms contributed to loyalty to the Bank

VARIABLE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Very Great Extent	77	30%
Great Extent	73	28%
Some Extent	68	26%
Little Extent	9	3%
No Extent	33	13%
Total	260	100%

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Data presented in Table 6 shows that a significant number of respondents, 77 (30%) and 73 (28%) respondents claimed that Access Bank's use of social media for customer relations strategies contributed to their loyalty to a very great extent and great extent respectively This shows that the majority of the respondents admitted that Access Bank's use of social media for customer relations were very effective.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed the extensive utilisation of various social media platforms by AAUA students to get information about Access Bank with Twitter emerging as the primary source for information about Access Bank, followed by LinkedIn and Facebook. The findings contradict Cadet (2016)'s assertion that many companies turn to Facebook as an advertising medium because of its high traffic and wider reach (Cadet, 2016). In the case of Access Bank, Twitter is the primary source is disseminating formation to its customers although the bank adopted other platforms to reach her customers. Also, students' diverse subscription patterns to Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube, and LinkedIn indicate a willingness to adopt multiple technologies for interaction. This resonates with Technology Determinism Theory propositions that emphasise on how the media influences how people think and behave and how societies functions as they transition from one technological period to the other (Asak & Ohiagun, 2013). Srinivasan & Rani (2020) highlights how these technological advancements are reshaping the future of banking by making services more accessible and efficient. New technology has made it possible to relate with diverse customers on a variety of electronic devices at the same time.

Further findings revealed that the majority of respondents agreed that AAUA's use of social media platforms for customer relations is positive as it helps in faster response, more engaging content, enhanced customer interaction & improved clarity in communications. This is in line with Customer Relations Management (CRM) theory which underscores the importance of managing customer perceptions and understanding customer needs to build lasting relationships. This approach acknowledges the diverse preferences among AAUA students, contributing to positive customer experiences, and potentially fostering long-term relationships.

Findings also indicated that majority of respondents claimed loyalty due to social media engagement as AAUA students admitted that to a great extent, Access Bank's use of social media for customer relations was very effective. The positive correlation suggests that Access Bank's social media efforts contribute significantly to customer retention, reinforcing the idea that well-managed interactions on social platforms can influence customers' long-term commitment. Findings from this study collaborates with Chukwu (2014)'s suggestion that conventional organisations should cooperate with new media technologies in order to improve on their operations.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study unveiled the significance of effective public relations strategies in shaping positive perceptions and fostering loyalty among customers. This study highlighted the substantial engagement of young adults (AAUA students) with multiple social media platforms and the pivotal role these platforms play in disseminating information about Access Bank. Findings showed that majority expressed effectiveness and satisfaction on Access Bank's social media use in engaging customers and fostering positive relationships, thereby indicating a promising avenue for the bank to further enhance its customer engagement strategies.

Based on the findings, it is recommended that Access Bank should consider diversifying its content strategy on social media to better cater to the customers' preferences. Recognising the varying impact levels of distinct content types, including industry news, financial advice, promotions, and customer success stories, can be instrumental in engaging a broader audience. Moreso, continual evaluation and refinement of social media

strategies are essential for sustained success. Access Bank should prioritise ongoing monitoring of user feedback, engagement metrics, and evolving trends to adapt and improve its social media approach.

References

- Asak, M. O., & Ohiagu, O. P. (2013). *Digital communication, new media theories and ethics: An introductory text*. Uche Business Service 2020.
- Bhole, L. (2006). *Financial institutions and markets: Structure, growth and innovations* (4th ed.). McGraw Hill Publishing Company Ltd.
- Cadet, F. O. (2016). *Business research methods* (3rd Ed.). Oxford University Press.
- Davis, R., & Anderson, M. (2019). Enhancing financial literacy through social media: A case study of Access Bank's social media platforms. *Journal of Finance and Economics*, 18(3), 234-256.
- Duhan, P., Jayakumar, N., & Bhaskar, A. (2013). *Social media analytics: Making sense of user comments*. IBM Global Business Services.
- Eling, M., & Lehmann, M. (2017). Regulatory challenges posed by fintech. *Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance: Issues and Practice*, 42(3), 386-409.
- Gupta, A., Brooks, J., & Gupta, R. (2019). A survey of social media and its security issues. *Procedia Computer Science*, 167, 167-174.
- Haron, H., Ismail, N. A., Rahman, A. A., & Napiyah, M. Z. (2018). Social media in the banking sector: Evidence from emerging economies. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 40, 268-276.
- Hong, S. (2012). Online news on customer relations among banks *Journal of Information Management*, 2 (6) 121-134
- Iteghie, J. E., & Iteghie, E. (2020). Social media and customer relationship management in Nigerian banks: An empirical analysis of customers' perspectives. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research*, 13(2), 50-61.
- Khanna, U., & Swaminathan, V. (2019). How do social media influencers shape consumers' product purchase decisions? An investigation of the impact of informational and normative appeals. *Journal of Business Research*, 101, 564-573.
- Kent, A., & Leaver, N. (2014). Network theory and small groups. *Small Group Research*, 35(3), 307-332.

- Kim, H. S., Kim, Y. S., & An, J. A. (2008). The effect of CRM system and CRM capabilities on customer-centric behavior in banks. *The Service Industries Journal*, 28(6), 689-704.
- Marques, O. (2016). *Innovative technologies in everyday life*. Springer.
- Mullings, B. (2005). Effective customer relations. Retrieved from <http://altavista.com/customerrelations/147>
- Ngai, E. W., Tao, S. S., & Moon, K. K. (2017). Social media research: Theories, constructs, and conceptual frameworks. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(3), 190-201.
- Reynolds, J. (2002). *A practical guide to CRM*. Os-borne/McGraw-Hill.
- Sanda, G. (2006). *Evaluation of customer relations strategies of selected banks in Nigeria*. Ibadan.
- Srinivasan, P., & Rani, D. R. (2020). Chatbots in banking: Understanding customer acceptance and expectations. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 57, 102176.
- Sheth, J. N., Sisodia, R. S., & Sharma, A. (2021). The antecedents and consequences of customer-centric marketing. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 49(3), 279-295.
- Sigala, M., Christou, E., & Gretzel, U. (2019). *Social media in travel, tourism and hospitality: Theory, practice and cases*. Academic Press.
- Smith, M. (2022). Building a sense of community through social media: The case of Access Bank. *Journal of Community Engagement*, 75(3), 321-335.
- Yu, Y., Duan, W., & Cao, Q. (2013). The impact of social and conventional media on firm equity value: A sentiment analysis approach. *Decision Support Systems*, 55(4), 919-926.